

SCENARIO A

TRUST BUILDING AMONG SHORT FOOD VALUE CHAIN ACTORS

This Scenario uses a digital tool to strengthen connections across the short food value chain, thereby **building trust** through visibility among food value chain actors and consumers.

FOCUS

Strengthening connections between actors in the short value chain

DIGITAL TOOL

A lean, standardised, and user-friendly digital representation of local farms, improving visibility and building trust among farmers, retailers, and consumers

FOR WHOM IS IT APPLICABLE?

- The actor is located in a short food value chain.
- Direct relationships with buyers and consumers are beneficial.
- Actors of the value chain are not aware of each other due to the lack of public visibility.

Implementation Pathway

STAGE 1: PREPARATION

- **Assess** published and unpublished information about your operation on existing digital platforms (e.g. CAP platform)
- **Assess** potential risks like increased public scrutiny or bureaucratic burden.
- **Discuss** with the technology provider regarding the integration

STAGE 2: GETTING STARTED

- Access the digital tool and learn its features.
- Verify that your farm or production info is accurate and up to date.
- Submit any additional relevant data.

STAGE 3: INTEGRATION

- Direct contact is created between producers, retailers, businesses, and consumers.
- The information becomes visible through initial interactions with short value chain actors.
- The local public learns about local food producers.

MAIN STRATEGIC CONSIDERATIONS

- Consider disclosing the already existing information on your current practices.
- Increased visibility may generate greater interest and more interaction requests.

WHAT IS ENABLED?

Visibility is improved through a simple, standardized, and user-friendly digital representation of local farms, **which enhances transparency and fosters trust.**

SCENARIO B

COLLECTIVE BRANDING FOR LARGE FOOD MANUFACTURING FIRMS

This Scenario uses a data platform with an integrated AI Agent for coordinated communication and **unified storytelling**, creating a credible picture of the sector.

FOCUS

Creating shared visibility and a coordinated, unified story across the ecosystem

DIGITAL TOOL

A data platform with an incorporated AI Agent to synthesise credible information into a cohesive story

FOR WHOM IS IT APPLICABLE?

- The sector is criticized for issues caused by some actors, and can't address sector-wide issues collectively.
- Individual stories regarding the same topic are varied in the value chain.

Implementation Pathway

STAGE 1: PREPARATION

- Identify what collective branding intends to challenge (misinformation, disinformation, etc.).
- Assess practices that can be used to aggregate the collective story, and combat false or harmful information about the food sector.

STAGE 2: GETTING STARTED

- Gather the evidence of these practices.
- Identify your individual contribution, contact potential actors and technology provider to outline ideas for the collective branding together.
- Ensure your information and documentation align with the shared vision of collective branding.

STAGE 3: INTEGRATION

- Participation in shaping the unified collective story becomes a regular part of your communication approach.
- Some false and harmful information about the industry is tackled, and the renewed collective branding starts being acknowledged and recognised.

MAIN STRATEGIC CONSIDERATIONS

- Mutual understanding of "collective branding" among actors is necessary.
- A digital tool should enhance rather than replace individual presence.

WHAT IS ENABLED?

Individual messages are synthesised into a **cohesive narrative** which collectively **debunks myths** without requiring actors to surrender their individual identities.

SCENARIO C

EMPOWERMENT OF SMALL FOOD PRODUCERS

This Scenario **equips** less-advantaged food producers with **technological and organizational capabilities**

Implementation Pathway

STAGE 1: PREPARATION

- Assess the most pressing constraints (time, technical skills and equipment, knowledge etc.)
- Identify what kind of support would be most helpful
- Evaluate what practices would be valuable to make visible.

STAGE 2: GETTING STARTED

- Get familiar with the digital tool and find the features that are most relevant to the identified challenges.
- Educate yourself to make informed decisions based on the data generated from the digital tool.

STAGE 3: INTEGRATION

- Your initial engagement with the digital tool becomes regular (e.g. automated digital documentation).
- The visualized and cumulative data will become company asset, which can be used for business and communication purposes.
- Organizational capability begins to build as engagement with the digital tool progresses.

FOCUS

Targeted support for less-advantaged actors within the value chain

DIGITAL TOOL

A digital tool allowing the collection, management and analysis of the necessary data to strengthen production, organisational, and communication capabilities.

FOR WHOM IS IT APPLICABLE?

- You are a small food producer with limited capacity and resources.
- Sustainable practices are present, but the resources to document and communicate them are limited.
- Decision-making is not possible due to the lack of knowledge or technical capabilities.

MAIN STRATEGIC CONSIDERATIONS

- It is important to begin with the most pressing capability you want to build.
- Having identified what matters most, it is important to proceed consistently.

WHAT IS ENABLED?

The intervention provides digital tools to **gather data for optimizing** production, and supports organization to build technological and organizational capabilities.